

Climate change impacts on health, economy and environment based on Bayesian and causal inference methods

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Abstract

As climate change progresses, there are powerful impacts on economy, environment and the health of various human communities. There are for example serious consequences on the large agricultural human communities around the globe due to climate-related agricultural disruptions, such as increasingly severe droughts or flooding, which finally beyond of the increased economical and environmental problems result also in a rise of health problems of the farming communities. This paper develops 4 effective tools that use causal inference methods or Bayesian regression models to assess the economic impacts of climate change on the health of the farming communities pertaining to the death of the farmers due to a mental health crunch. A relevant case study covering a large region area and population (i.e. India) is shown which establishes the feasibility of our concept, as the paper reveals the complex relationships between the climate change consisting for example of increasing of maximum temperatures and/or decreasing of the maximum levels of precipitations across the recent years (2010-2021), with effects on the economic stability consisting of decreasing of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from agriculture across the same period of time (2010-2021), and which finally result in worsening of the health outcome mentioned above. Therefore, the paper creates the tools necessary for the evidence-based decision policymakers who need to take the appropriate measures in order to tackle the negative effects that these complex relationships between climate change, economic instability, and health could produce on the vulnerable agricultural human communities.

1. Introduction

Climate change has become a recognized global issue, which is affecting many regions and countries around the globe [1-6]. As it moves forward, one of its harmful impacts is a rise in the health problems among farming communities [7-16]. Such health problems could be related to heat-related illnesses (heat cramps, heat exhaustion, heat syncope, heat stroke, death) [17-26], related to respiratory systems [27, 28], liver or kidney disease, exposure to gastrointestinal illness like diarrhea, exposure to waterborne pathogens (bacteria, viruses, and parasites) and other health problems [7]: measles, guinea worm infestation, malaria, cholera,

cerebro-spinal meningitis. The health problems could be also the ones not directly tied to climate change, such as mental health problems (e.g. alcoholism, anxiety, depression, etc) in farming communities [8-16]. These mental health problems are sometimes a consequence of financial stress [15] and indirectly connected to the climate related agricultural disruptions, such as increasingly severe droughts, water scarcity, severe fires, flooding, catastrophic storms (e.g. hurricanes, tornados) and declining biodiversity. Therefore there is a dire need for evidence-based policy decisions, which to tackle the complex relationships between climate change, economic instability and poverty, and mental health outcomes in these vulnerable farming communities [8,29,30].

The paper develops innovative tools that use causal inference methods [31,32] and Bayesian regression models [33,34] to assess the economic impact of climate change on mental health of farming communities. The developed tools will use data on climate change such as either the yearly maximum temperature recorded for a region/state/district, or the yearly maximum precipitation recorded for a region/state/district, or the yearly minimum Standardised Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) [35] recorded for a region/state/district. The SPEI index takes into account the precipitation and the potential EvapoTranspiration (PET) in determining drought, while PET is given by the combination of the water lost through the evaporation at the surface of earth and the water lost through transpiration by plants through its own tissues and water vessels. The data on the climate change will be integrated with other datasets such as the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from agriculture, the farming irrigation covering areas, the indebtedness of farmers, and the health outcome to provide an understanding of these interconnected issues.

The studied health outcome in this paper consists of the death of the farmers due to a mental health crunch.

A relevant case study is used (i.e. India) consisting of a large region area (i.e. 3,287,263 km²) and population (i.e. 1,428,627,663) to evaluate the developed decision tools, while a recent period of time is chosen (i.e. 2010 to 2021) which is relevant for the study because of the climate change and the effects it produced. Especially the country of India has been powerfully affected by climate change in the last 20 years especially because of severe droughts but also other extreme events such as flooding, sever fires or water scarcity. In this work, India comprises about 36 states and union territories [35] but several territories are excluded because they are either islands (Andaman and Nicobar islands, Lakshadweep archipelago), small cities or territories with little or no farming available (Dadra and Nagar Haveli and Daman and Diu, Chandigarh) or states for which data could not be made available at the time of this study (Ladakh, West Bengal, Odisha, Gujarat): this leads to 28 states left to

be investigated in this work which are Delhi, Haryana, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Puducherry, Tamilnadu, Chhattishgarh, Telengana, Andhra Pradesh, Goa, Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Rajasthan, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh, Sikkim, Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Nagaland, Manipur, Mizoram, Tripura, Meghalaya, Bihar, Jammu and Kashmir.

The goal of the work is to empower policymakers with precise insights that can lead to the formulation of impactful policies to mitigate against the pressing climate issues and their effects on the considered mental health outcome, which is death of the farmers due to a mental health crunch.

The causal inference methods is the first set of mathematical models used in this work and it will consist of the Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) method [31,32], which will further result in the following mathematical models: (I) the linear model, (II) the multiple linear model and (III) a more complex multiple linear model which will include risk and moderator type of variables. Causal inference and DAGs have been used successfully in recent studies of climate change impacts on environment [37-39] or in medical epidemiology [40].

The second set of mathematical models will be the Bayesian regression models, which will consist of the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation with Bayesian Regression Univariate method and software package (INLABRU) [33,34]. This method showed recently very good results in literature when modelling climate variables with a spatiotemporal distribution [41, 42]. Therefore, in this work there are chosen these two mathematical formalisms (i.e. causal inference and Bayesian regression models) in order to study the relationships between the climate change, the economic instability and poverty, and the considered health outcome.

The paper is structured as follows: section 2 presents in more detailed the climate change problem and its implications on economic stability and health. Section 3 presents the mathematical methods developed or used in this work. Section 4 shows the numerical results. Last section 5 is for discussion and conclusions.

2. Climate change impacts on health, economy and environment

Climate change consisted over the last twenty years of severe phenomena such as global land and ocean temperature increases, rising sea levels, ice loss at Earth's poles and in mountain glaciers but also extreme weather events such as droughts, dry climate, wild fires, floods, storms and extreme temperatures. Therefore climate change has been and continues to be a vast scientific and research subject with large implications on human life. Some of the

effects on economy and especially agriculture, environment and human health, will be briefly discusses in this section as it will be not enough space to commensurate this entire subject. It will be mentioned also some of the mathematical models employed in the previous works for quantifying these effects. Furthermore, a case study will be used here and covering a large geographical area (i.e. India) in order to exemplify the situation developed in the last two decades due to climate change. The numerical effects due to climate change on economy and health will be determined in chapter 3.

2.1 Climate change manifestations

First, while looking to the climate change phenomena beyond the extreme events that have been mentioned already (droughts, dry climate, wild fires, floods, storms and extreme temperatures), there has been an increased of the Earth average surface temperature of about 1.5 °C since the beginning of XX century [43]. This phenomenon has dramatically accentuated over the last twenty years all over the planet Earth. For the case study of India, which covers a large geographically area (i.e. 3,287,263 km²) and strongly affected by climate change, Figure 1 shows the yearly minimum SPEI index between 2010 and 2021 taken from [44]: for each year between 2010 and 2021 it is used for 33 main Indian states the yearly minimum value of SPEI index because the lower index values correspond to drier climates (i.e. droughts), while higher index values correspond to humid climate, and the interest in this section is in climate changes consisting of drier climates and droughts.

Figure 1. Yearly minimum value of SPEI index between 2010 and 2021 in India.

The United States Drought Monitor (USDM) classification system recognizes the worst droughts termed as ‘exceptional drought’ for a SPEI index below -2 [45]: the full USDM classification is exceptional drought for -2 or less, extreme drought for -1.6. to -1.99, severe drought for -1.3 to -1.59, moderate drought for -0.8 to -1.29, abnormally drought for -0.5 to -0.79 and normal or wet conditions for -0.49 or above. Therefore it can be observed that droughts affected India for the entire period of time 2010 to 2021 because the yearly minimum SPEI index was below -2 for the entire period of time. Furthermore, this can be also noticed in Figure 2 where the maximum temperatures across all India were above 45 °C, and especially for the years 2010 and 2016 there were very high temperatures of 47 °C. The maximum precipitations were also not that high for the respective two years (i.e. below 3200 mm), which indicates that most probably droughts took place in these two years 2010 and 2016. This is confirmed also in literature [46] and with what actually happened during the respective years 2010 and 2016.

Figure 2. Maximum temperatures and maximum precipitation for India between 2010 and 2021.

At a geospatial level, Figure 3 shows how the maximum temperatures, the maximum precipitation and the yearly minimum SPEI index vary across the entire considered region (i.e. India) and for the entire period of time 2010 and 2021. There are high levels of maximum temperatures (i.e. dark red colour) at the geospatial level for the period of time 2010 to 2021 consisting of temperatures above 45 °C. If this is corroborated with the maximum level of precipitations, which seemed to occur in the South-West part of India, it may lead to the assumption that the states in the South-East (i.e. Andhra Pradesh and

Tamilnadu), which do not receive the highest level of precipitation, in the Central part of India (i.e. Madhya Pradesh, Telengana, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and Maharashtra - coloured in dark red in Figure 3a), and Rajasthan might be the ones mostly affected by dry climate and droughts.

a) Maximum Temperatures (°C)

b) Maximum Precipitation (mm)

c) Minimum SPEI index

Figure 3. Geospatial distribution of the the maximum temperatures, the maximum precipitation and the yearly minimum SPEI index over the entire period of time 2010 and 2021.

It is clearly that the climate change manifestations in India have been evidenced through powerful droughts, which took place starting with 2010 and which might have affected the economy, the health and the environment as it will be seen in the following sections.

2.2 Climate change effects on economy and agriculture

The important effects of climate change that already had or that will have on the economy and specifically on the agricultural sub-domain have been discussed since more than two decades ago [47]. It was envisaged that overall the agricultural productivity will be affected and especially in the tropical regions and that adaptations measures will need to be adopted on different time length scales (i.e. short-term, medium-term and long-term). Therefore, there are macroeconomics effects (GDP growth, inflation and interest rates) [48], microeconomics effects (changes in supply and demand, taxes and regulations) [49], changes in the agricultural environment (humidity, temperature, rainfall and light intensity) [50], effects on the agricultural productivity [51], effects on the agricultural diversity of the farmer units (property ownership, number of productive hectares, type of systems implemented) [51] or changes in crop management practices [52]. The agriculture infrastructure includes the off-farm infrastructure (e.g. transport systems including roads and bridges) and the on-farm infrastructure (e.g. irrigation systems including dams, tube wells). While the transport system can be affected for example by floods, then the on-farm infrastructure can be affected by droughts [53]. For example, droughts affect the irrigation facilities [54,55] because of lack of water and which will further result in low crop yields, wasted seeds or agrochemicals and loss of production. The economical effect will be low return on investments due to the increased costs with the irrigation systems or decreasing income because of loss of production, which may finally result in increased levels of poverty and even bankruptcy of the farmers. This might be possible to be seen for example in the decrease of the agricultural revenues in the total GDP of a country or at the level of region/state/province/division from a country.

Based on the above explanations, it is would be useful to look to the GDP from agriculture of a given region over a period of time and to identify any correlations with the extreme weather events such as droughts or floods. For the example of India, climate change manifestations or even more simply the climate impacts on agriculture have been seen very detrimental with regard to the crop grown, the insect pest infestation, the cropping pattern, the grain yield quantity and quality and other characteristics (e.g. straw yield obtained, intensity of weeds, overall health of the crop, etc) [56-59]. Therefore, Figure 4 shows the minimum, the maximum GDP (i.e. in Lakh) obtained from agriculture for India between 2010 and 2021 together with the maximum level of credits (i.e. in Crore) given to farmers during the same period of time. Several numerical values are divided by 60 hence the term

min used in the Figure 4. For two Indian states (Madhya Pradesh and Maharashtra), which have maximum levels of GDP from agriculture, they seem to have also some counter-performances consisting of lower GDP from agriculture based on a comparison of the intensity of the dark red colour between Figure 4a and Figure 4b. Furthermore, another list of four states does not have either maximum or minimum points but it scores in both criteria that is high but also low GDP from agriculture, which high and low peaks might be influenced/determined by climate change: Karnataka, Tamilnadu, Andhra Pradesh and Rajasthan. On another hand, states like Tamilnadu, Andhra Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh seem to have the highest levels of credits given to farmers over the period of time 2010 to 2021, which credits are many times used for irrigations in order to combat dry climate and droughts. If it is to summarize the states identified in this section and to compare with the ones from previous section 2.1, it can be observed similarities as shown in Figure 5.

a) Minimum GDP from agriculture
(i.e. in Lakh)

b) Maximum GDP from agriculture
(i.e. in Lakh)

c) Maximum credits given to farmers.
(i.e. in Crore)

Figure 4. Minimum, maximum GDP from agriculture and maximum credits given to farmers between 2010 and 2021 in India.

Figure 4. Comparison between the lists of Indian states possibly affected by droughts and devised based on inspecting the temperatures/precipitation/SPEI maps (section 2.1) and the economical devised list based on GDP from agriculture and credits given to farmers.

2.3. Climate change effects on environment

The effects of climate change on weather and environment are massive, and they are putting at risk the lives and the subsistence of many millions if not even billions of people [1-

5]. Moreover, the economic reverberations of the large number of intricacies related to climate change might not even be possible to be fully evaluated at the present time [6]. What is sure is that as the temperatures are increasing it is producing changes in the weather consisting of extreme events such as droughts, hurricanes and floods, which are also more powerful and harder to predict. Moreover, the same or different and multiple extreme events (e.g. both droughts and floods) may produce at the same geographical location. As a consequence of all these climacteric changes, the planet has already warmed about 1.5 °C since the beginning of previous century [43] and if the causes of climate change are not at least diminished (i.e. mainly consisting of the burning of fossil fuels such as oil, gas and coal) then this global warming may continue together with its disastrous effects on the environment: melting sea ice, sea level rise with all its consequences (e.g. damaging infrastructure like roads, erosion of coastal ecosystems, coastal flooding), warmer ocean waters and marine heat waves (e.g. plankton and marine mammals extinction), pollution and irrespirable air, ecosystem damaging (e.g. pests, pathogen infections), effects on animals (e.g. again risk of extinction), effects on agriculture (e.g. destruction of entirely or partly of the agriculture soil and/or crops, decimation of livestock) and not at last effects on humans (e.g. displacement, injury, famine, diseases such as respiratory diseases [27,28] or heat-related illnesses [17-26] and even death).

It is clearly that the effects of climate change on the environment are large such as desertification in case of multiple droughts or destruction entirely or partly of the land in case of flooding or erosion of coastal ecosystems and coastal flooding. Consequently, this can affect the agriculture as well [60], which needs to adopt resilience measures such as increasing the amount and efficiency of irrigations [61-63] and water storage systems. However, the increase of irrigation may affect the available water resources [64-66] and therefore once again the need for more efficient irrigation systems.

Figure 5 shows how the maximum gross irrigation (i.e. in thousands hectares) varied per year between 2010 and 2021 for India. Gross irrigation is the total surface area being irrigated while taken into account if multiple similar or different crops were irrigated on the same area within a year. Figure 5 shows a steep increase of the maximum gross irrigated areas between 2010 and 2021, which could be put on several reasons such as more investments in agriculture but also on adoption of measures against the climate change consisting of dry climate and droughts during the respective period of time. Furthermore, Figure 6 shows at the geospatial level the maximum gross irrigated areas (i.e. in thousands hectares) for India for the entire period 2010 to 2021. Several states have used more irrigation than others namely Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan while another set of states have used also

more irrigation and are spotted also by their bigger size, which are Maharashtra, Karnataka, Tamilnadu, Andhra Pradesh and Telengana. If it is to compare this list of states supposedly affected by droughts and dry climate with the lists shown previously in Figure 4, it will be noticed very good similarities as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 5. Variation of the maximum gross irrigated area per year in India between 2010 and 2021 in India (i.e. in thousands hectares).

Figure 6. The maximum gross irrigated area (i.e. in thousands hectares) shown at the spatial level for India for the entire period between 2010 and 2021.

Figure 7. Comparison between the lists of Indian states possibly affected by droughts and devised based on inspecting the temperatures/precipitation/SPEI maps (section 2.1) and the economical devised list based on maximum GDP obtained from agriculture and credits given to farmers (section 2.2) and the present list devised based on inspecting the maximum gross irrigated area between 2010 and 2021.

2.4 Climate change effects on health

There could be a large spectrum of health problems that can be attributed to climate change phenomena (e.g. severe droughts, water scarcity, severe fires, flooding, catastrophic storms, etc) and that can negatively affect the farmers [7-16] such as: heat-related illnesses (heat cramps, heat exhaustion, heat syncope, heat stroke, death) [17-26], respiratory related diseases [27, 28], liver or kidney disease, exposure to gastrointestinal illness like diarrhea, exposure to waterborne pathogens and other health problems [7] (e.g. measles, guinea worm infestation, malaria, cholera, cerebro-spinal meningitis, etc). This work is interested in mental health problems (e.g. alcoholism, anxiety, depression, etc) due to climate change and affecting farming communities [8-16], and which sometimes could be also aggravated by financial stress [15].

Therefore, the studied health outcome is the death of the farmers due to a mental health crunch. This health risk has become recently part of a research subject entitled Diseases Of Despair (DoD) [67,68], which typically include mental health issues (e.g. depression, anxiety, substance abuse, etc). The mental health of farmers is the outcome of a complex combination of social, environmental and economic factors [69].

The most prominent social factors discussed also in the literature are 1) poverty [70-74], 2) pesticide exposure and poisoning [75,76], substance abuse, 3) illiteracy/education [77,78], 4) overwork and heavy workload/stress/hazards in farming [79,80], 4) lack of skilled labour,

5) poor living conditions [81,82], 6) time pressure [83], 7) previous existing health problems (i.e. mental problems, obesity, metabolic syndrome, abdominal adiposity, cardiovascular disease, higher body mass index BMI, poor sleep quality, musculoskeletal disorders, cuts, fractures) [84-92], 8) previous injuries (i.e. including neck, shoulder, and back pains).

The environmental effects have been discussed before and they include climate variability like droughts (including solar radiance exposure) or flooding [47,50,51,53,69,70]: for example higher temperatures above 40 degrees Celsius for longer periods of time (i.e. weeks) will produce droughts, which will affect directly the health of agriculture workers and indirectly, by destroying the economy, affecting again the wealth and health (i.e. mental health) of agriculture workers and farmers.

The economical factors may include 1) indebtedness [69,93,94], 2) lack of agricultural investment and irrigation improvement (i.e. only 51% of land used for agriculture in India is irrigated) [52,54,55,70], use of cash crops (higher costs) as opposed to food crops [57], 3) increased use of noninstitutional credit sources [8.70,93,94], 4) lack of subsidiary occupations with worsening the situation that marginal and small farmers to be submerged by high interest loans and crop yield volatility, 5) poor agricultural extension services/contact, taxes and governmental regulations, 6) poor access to market information, 7) poor road infrastructure, 8) unfavourable market prices [48,49,95-99], 9) poor access to market information, 10) electricity irrigation costs, 11) crop failure, 12) psychological stress associated with coping with the regulatory framework, 13) fragmented and small land holding makes farming a risky economical proposition even under the best of conditions, 14) small land holdings stop benefiting from mechanization, 15) lack of modern irrigation, and other investment-based technological improvements, 16) productivity being suboptimal, 17) the government-administered minimum support price may not even cover the cost of production, usage of expensive [48,49,95-99], 18) commercial hybrid seeds in place of cheaper and hardier home-grown ones.

For India some of these social, economical and environmental effects and their various combinations have been addressed in the literature [56-60, 70, 75, 100], while this work presents a new approach through causal inference methods and Bayesian regression models.

Figure 8 shows the geospatial distribution of the total number of deaths of farmers due to a mental health crunch in India between 2010 and 2021. Three states can be identified as having the highest numbers Maharashtra (36807), Karnataka (17607) and Andhra Pradesh (13517). Table 1 shows the full list of Indian states and of the total death outcome for the period 2010 to 2021. If one takes the state with the highest number (i.e. Maharashtra ~36807) as a reference, then the list of states, which could be called statistical significant at

the- level of 5% are in order Karnataka (17607), Andhra Pradesh (13517), Madhya Pradesh (9138), Telengana (6434), Kerala (4998), Chhattishgarh (4422), Uttar Pradesh (3671), Tamilnadu (3476), Gujarat (3211) and West Bengal (2030). This new list based solely on the considered health outcome shows some degree of similarity with the lists from Figure 7 based either on the temperatures/precipitation/SPEI maps (section 2.1), the list based on maximum GDP obtained from agriculture and credits given to farmers (section 2.2) and the list devised based on inspecting the maximum gross irrigated area between 2010 and 2021 (section 2.3), and which are summarized in Figure 9.

Figure 8. Geospatial distribution of total number of deaths of farmers due to a mental health crunch in India between 2010 and 2021.

Figure 9. Comparison between the lists of Indian states possibly affected by droughts and devised based on inspecting the maximum gross irrigated area between 2010 and 2021 and the present list based on the health outcome for the same period of time.

Furthermore, Figure 10 shows how the health outcome varied in time between 2010 and 2021 for the three Indian states (Maharashtra, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh) which had the highest numbers. A common trend consisting of higher values before 2014 and smaller values after 2016 can be observed for these states. This possibly suggests the existence of some common factors, and one of these factors could be the weather patterns resulting from climate change, which included the droughts before year 2014.

a) Maharashtra

b) Karnataka

c) Andhra Pradesh

Figure 10. Health outcome variation in time between 2010 and 2021 for the three Indian states (Maharashtra, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh) with the highest numbers.

Table 1. Full list of Indian states and of the total death outcome for the period 2010 to 2021.

	Indian state (in bold states with high output rate)	Outcome variable per total (2010- 2021)	Scores of 20 important states
1	Andaman & Nicobar	NA	-
2	Chandigarh	0	-
3	Daman and Diu and Dadra and Nagar Haveli	78	-
4	Delhi	48	-
5	Haryana	1625	6
6	Jharkhand	556	4
7	Karnataka	17607	19
8	Kerala	4998	15
9	Lakshadweep	NA	-
10	Madhya Pradesh	9138	17
11	Maharashtra	36807	20
12	Odisha	774	5
13	Puducherry	34	-
14	Tamilnadu	3476	12
15	Chhattishgarh	4422	14
16	Telangana	6434	16
17	Andhra Pradesh	13517	18
18	Puducherry	34	-
19	Goa	18	-
20	Himachal Pradesh	318	3
21	Punjab	1812	9
22	Rajasthan	1680	7
23	Gujarat	3211	11
24	Uttarakhand	95	-
25	Uttar Pradesh	3671	13
26	Sikkim	172	-
27	Assam	1732	8
28	Arunachal Pradesh	99	-
29	Nagaland	14	-
30	Manipur	10	-
31	Mizoram	84	-
32	Tripura	237	1
33	Meghalaya	67	-
34	West Bengal	2030	10
35	Bihar	390	2
36	Ladakh	NA	-
37	Jammu and Kashmir	124	-

A very low threshold of 15 events per year is used, which for the entire period of 12 years (2010 to 2021) would results in a threshold of at least 200 deaths due to the mental crunch. Function of this threshold, the following list of 20 main states (i.e. henceforth identified as the list) where farmers most likely would be affected by droughts can be devised, and it is shown below in a descending order and starting from the states with the highest numbers. A score is assigned also to each such state function of the descending position in the list: Maharashtra (20), Karnataka (19), Andhra Pradesh (18), Madhya Pradesh (17), Telengana (16), Kerala (15), Chhattishgarh (14), Uttar Pradesh (13), Tamilnadu (12),

Gujarat (11), West Bengal (10), Punjab (9), Assam (8), Rajasthan (7), Haryana (6), Odisha (5), Jharkhand (4), Himachal Pradesh (3), Bihar (2), Tripura (1).

Based on the findings uncovered in sections 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4, Figure 11 shows how the effects because of the social, economical and environmental causes and thier interactions due to climate change, may affect the lives of farming communities in India.

The long-term consequences of climate change on agriculture may consist of water shortage and increased demand, soil erosion, decreased soil fertility, displacement of farmer community or risk to food security.

The short-term consequences of climate change on agriculture may consist of drought, flooding, crop failure, soil erosion, heat stress in livestock, pest and disease outbreak, water shortage. The long and short term consequences will affect the economy by decreasing the GDP obtained from agriculture, food insecurity and economic instability. The direct effects of climate change on health of farmers and the indirect effects of GDP from agriculture on the health of farmers will result in a large set of medical problems covering the mental health problems (e.g. alcoholism, anxiety, depression, etc), the heat-related illnesses (heat cramps, heat exhaustion, heat syncope, heat stroke, death), the ones related to respiratory systems, liver or kidney disease, gastrointestinal illness like diarrhea, exposure to waterborne pathogens (bacteria, viruses, and parasites) and other health problems (measles, guinea worm infestation, malaria, cholera, cerebro-spinal meningitis, etc).

Figure 11. The social, economical and environmental effects and their interactions due to climate change and how may affect the lives of farming communities.

3. Causal Inference methods and Bayesian regression models for assessing the effects of climate change on health, economy and environment

There are various methods to assess the effect of one or more independent variables on to other dependent variables and which are all part of a more complex interconnected network system such as the causal inference methods or the Bayesian regression models.

The first set of methods discussed is the causal inference methods [31,32] and it may include models like the causal pie model, the structural equation modelling, the Rubin causal model or the Pearl's structural causal model. In the context of the epidemiological and health medical domains, the causal inference has been used to study the effect of a treatment on a set of patients with several specific symptoms, which were produced by some unseen causes.

More recently, the causal inference has been used to study the effects of climate change on the health [101,102] or the agricultural systems [29,30]. In this paper, in a more novel context it is studied the interaction between the climate change, the economy and their effects on the health by using a specific class of causal inference methods named the Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs). The DAGs are defined by a set of vertices (V) representing all the relevant variables, and a set of directed edges E, which will connect the vertices V. In general, the variables shown in a DAG (Figure 12) could be the exposures, which are the independent variable affecting other variables, the confounders, which are the common cause to several variables and are similar to exposure, or the risk factors which are also similar to exposure and are affecting the other variables.

There are also the mediators, which are variable affecting the direction and/or strength of the relationship between an independent variable and a dependent variable.

The moderators, which are the variables on the causal pathway from exposure to outcome.

Finally, the outcome variable of a DAG, which is the output dependent variable.

A moderator variable can be part of a DAG, and while in this work it is used the approach described in [103,104] when calculating the effect of the confounder on the mediator, it gives $\text{Confounder} * \text{Direct_effect}_1 * \text{Moderator} * \text{Moderator_effect}$, as shown also in Figure 12.

Based on existent literature for the domains of agriculture, climate change, health and interactions between those, Table A1 from the Appendix shows a comprehensive list of 15 variables together with the reasons for which they can be included in DAGs for studying the interactions between climate change, economical instability in the agriculture economical sector and health outcomes. These variables can be enumerated function of their type: the confounders, which are the climate variables comprising the maximum temperature of a geographical region (e.g. county, state, district, department), the maximum precipitation (e.g.

county, state, department, etc) for the respective region or the SPEI index for a region, county, state or department. Then, there is the mediator variable, which is the GDP obtained from agriculture.

The risks affecting the other variables could be the scale of agriculture (e.g. small cultivated land), education of farmers, characteristics of crops (e.g. cash crops), characteristics of the market, agricultural incentives, comorbidities of farmers, climate adaptation support, type of worker (land owners named cultivators, agricultural labourers). There are also moderator variables such as wealth (e.g. irrigation areas, wealth of farmers) and finally the health outcomes.

Figure. 12. First set of methods based on the DAG diagrams containing confounder, moderator, mediator, outcome and risk variables

The second set of methods used in this work is the Bayesian linear regression models [33,34]. In this type of models, one output variables is calculated as the linear mixture of several other input variables with the scope of determining the posterior probability distribution of the regression parameters so that in the end to be able to estimate out-of-sample values for the output variable, while assuming also some prior probabilities for the parameters. If the input variables are Gaussian (normal) distributed then it is obtained the normal linear model and in this work it will be used the INLABRU method and software package (INLABRU) [105-107] in order to calculate the regression parameters and the output variable.

3.1 DAGs based linear models

3.1.1 Linear model

The simplest DAGs that can exist are shown in Fig. 13 and describe the independent effect that a single input variable consisting for example of the maximum temperature can have on the health outcome and which can be implemented by a linear equation of type $y=m*x + n$ where x is the input variable, y is the output variable, m is the slope of the linear equation (i.e. call it direct effect), n is the intercept and $*$ is the multiplication sign. Three such linear equations will form the first and the simplest investigative model (i.e. consisting of three independent DAGs), which will be used in this work, and consisting of equations eq. (1) to (5).

Figure. 13. Three simple DAG diagrams each of them containing a single independent input variable and a single output variable as shown above: a) direct effect of input Maxim_Temperature variable (or Maximum_Precipitation variable, or SPEI variable) on Health Outcome variable, direct effect of Maximum_Temperature variable on GDP_from_agriculture variable and direct effect of GDP_from_agriculture on the Health_

outcome variable; b) positive direct effect of maximum temperature on the number of deaths due to farmers having a mental health crunch; c) negative effect of the maximum temperature on the GDP from agriculture.

$$\text{Health_outcome} = a * \text{Maximum_Temperature} + d_1 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{GDP_agriculture} = b * \text{Maximum_Temperature} + d_2 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Health_outcome} = c * \text{GDP_agriculture} + d_3 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Direct_effect}_{\text{MTHO}} = a \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Indirect_effect}_{\text{MTHO}} = b * c \quad (5)$$

where a , b and c are the slopes of the linear equations, d_{1-3} are the intercepts, $\text{Direct_effect}_{\text{MTHO}}$ is the direct effect that the single input Maximum Temperature variable has on the Health Outcome, $\text{Indirect_effect}_{\text{MTHO}}$ is the indirect effect which the Maximum Temperature variable would have on the health outcome if one would use the two independent eqs (2) and (3) and the two slopes b and c and would ignore eq.(1) for the sake of simplicity.

The direct effect ($\text{Direct_effect}_{\text{MTHO}}$) of the maximum temperature on the health outcome is simply the slope a from eq.(4).

The indirect effect ($\text{Indirect_effect}_{\text{MTHO}}$) of the maximum temperature on the health outcome via the GDP from agriculture equals the product of the two slopes b and c if one would ignore eq.(1) for the sake of simplicity and in order to avoid adding any more non-linearities in the calculation of $\text{Indirect_effect}_{\text{MTHO}}$.

The slope a in eq. (1) determines the quantity by which the health outcome increases (i.e. sign of a positive) or decreases (i.e. sign of a negative) for when the Maximum_Temperature variable varies with a quantity (e.g. unit value). This is the actual interpretation of the direct and indirect effects. Furthermore, for example, it can be seen in Fig.13(b) the positive direct effect (i.e. increasing slope line) of the maximum temperature on the number of deaths due to farmers having a mental health crunch. Furthermore, in Fig.13(c) the negative direct effect (i.e. decreasing slope line) of the maximum temperature on the GDP from agriculture can be seen.

3.1.2 Multiple linear model

Fig. 14 shows a slightly more complicated DAG in which all variables are interconnected and it includes a causal relationship between the climate change (i.e. increase/decrease of the

maximum temperature, or increase/decrease of the maximum precipitation, or increase/decrease of the SPEI value) and the economic instabilities (i.e. increase/decrease of the GDP from agriculture), and their effects on the health outcome (i.e. increase/decrease of the number of health events) and therefore using these three variables (i.e. the maximum precipitation, GDP from agriculture, health outcome).

Figure. 14. DAG diagram containing confounder (e.g. maximum temperature, maximum precipitation, SPEI), mediator (GDP from agriculture), outcome (health outcome): direct and indirect effects of maximum temperature on the health outcome are shown.

The effect of the confounder consisting of the maximum temperature on the GDP from agriculture is re-written below (Fig. 14):

$$\text{GDP_Agriculture} = b * \text{Maximum_Temperature} + d \quad (6)$$

where once again the slope of eq. (6) is b and it represents the effect of Maximum_Temperature variable on the GDP_Agriculture, d is the intercept.

Furthermore, it can be written the following equation which expresses the effect of both the confounder (Maximum_Temperature) and the mediator (GDP from agriculture) on the health outcome (Fig. 14):

$$\text{Health_outcome} = a * \text{Maximum_Temperature} + c * \text{GDP_Agriculture} + e \quad (7)$$

where c and a are the slopes and e is the intercept.

Eq.(7) represents a multiple linear equation where there are multiple (i.e. two) independent variables (Maximum_Temperature and GDP_Agriculture) that predict the dependent Health_outcome variable.

It can be now defined in the context of Fig. 14 the direct effect of the maximum temperature on the health outcome:

$$\text{Direct_Effect} = a \quad (8)$$

The indirect effect of the maximum temperature on the health outcome through the GDP from agriculture variable (Fig. 14) is now calculated as:

$$\text{Indirect_Effect} = b * c \quad (9)$$

Therefore eqs. (6) to (9) describe the second linear regression model, which will be used, if one uses either the maximum temperature or the maximum precipitation or the SPEI index as the confounder in Fig. 14.

3.1.3 Complex DAG multiple linear model

As already mentioned, a larger set of 15 variables have been identified based on literature that can be part of DAGs and describing the complex interactions between climate change, economical instability in the agriculture economical sector and the health outcomes. Table A1 from Appendix shows this extended list of 15 variables. Fig. 15 shows a complex DAG based on all the 15 variables identified from literature and shown in this Table A1 from Appendix. The strengths of the relationships between the variables are defined as d_1 to d_{16} , and while the number of variables (i.e 15) has increased, overall the interactions between the variables appear also now more intricate.

However, there is no data available for all these 15 variables in the literature and therefore based only on the data available in the literature, the extended set of 15 variables is pruned to a set of only 5 variables shown in the DAG from Fig.16(a), which is the third model which will be applied in this work and which will consist of eqs. (10) and (11). This third model is also characterized by the existence of a moderator variable, which is the irrigation area, for which the way of implementing it in a DAG it is discussed in the references [103,104].

Therefore, the third model consists of the eqs.(10) and (11) based on the DAG shown in Fig. 16(a):

$$\text{GDP_Agriculture} = d_2 * \text{Maximum_Temperature} + d_2 * \text{Climate} * d_6 * \text{Irrigation_area} + e_1 \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Health_outcome} = d_1 * \text{Maximum_Temperature} + d_3 * \text{GDP_Agriculture} + d_5 * \text{Credit_to_farmer} + e_2 \quad (11)$$

where d_1, d_2, d_3, d_4, d_5 represent the slopes and e_1 and e_2 are the intercepts (Figure 5).

The direct and indirect effects are calculated with the following equations for the model from Fig. 16(a):

$$\text{Direct_effect} = d_1 \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Indirect_effect} = d_2 * d_3 \quad (13)$$

If the moderator variable (i.e. irrigation area) is seen as a risk variable (i.e. as shown in Figure 16(b)) then while equation (11) will remain the same, then equation (10) will suffer some changes as shown below. Eqs. (12) and (13) will remain the same also for the model below shown also in Fig.16(b):

$$\text{GDP_Agriculture} = d_2 * \text{Maximum_Temperature} + d_2 * \text{Climate} + d_6 * \text{Irrigation_area} + e_1 \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Health_outcome} = d_1 * \text{Maximum_Temperature} + d_3 * \text{GDP_Agriculture} + d_5 * \text{Credit_to_farmer} + e_2 \quad (15)$$

Figure 15. Complex DAG based on all the 15 variables described in Table 1 from Appendix.

a) Irrigation area variable as a moderator variable

b) Irrigation area variable as a risk variable

Figure 16. DAGs based on variables described in Table 1 from Appendix and for which the source of data was available in the literature: irrigation_area and credit_to_farmers variables.

3.2 Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation with Bayesian Regression Univariate software package (INLABRU)

The fourth model is the INLABRU software package [105-107], which implements a class of methods for calculating inference in datasets that have spatial correlation in the observed variables and spatial structure in unobserved explanatory variables. The Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation method makes the Bayesian inference based on Laplace's method [104,105], while INLABRU [105] is a software package which makes an extension of the method for several purposes such as point process modelling or Bayesian spatial modelling with distance sampling data. The datasets used in this work whether related either to the health outcomes, climate data or the economic indices have all a spatial structure related to the geographical region(s) (e.g. county/state/department), which is understudied.

The scope of Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation method as described for example in [107] is to determine the vector of latent effects x from eq. (16), which are part of the linear predictor from eq. (17):

$$x = (\eta_1, \dots, \eta_n, \alpha, \beta_1, \dots) \quad (16)$$

$$\eta_i = \alpha + \sum_{j=1}^{n_\beta} \beta_j z_{ji} + \sum_{k=1}^{n_f} f^{(k)}(u_{ki}) + \varepsilon_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (17)$$

where η_i are the linear predictors, n is the number of observations, α is the intercept, β_j , $j=1,\dots,n_\beta$, coefficients of some covariates $\{z_j\}_{j=1}^{n_\beta}$, function $f^{(k)}$ defines n_f random effects of other vector of covariates $\{u_k\}_{k=1}^{n_f}$, ε_i is an error term that is not always present function of the likelihood to be optimized.

In [107] was proposed an approximation for the posterior distribution of the latent effects, which was computational superior to the other proposed solutions and consisted of a Laplacian approximation, which was equal to the product between the Gaussian approximation of the posterior distribution and an exponential of a spline function of the latent effects:

$$\pi_{LA}(x_i|\theta, y) \propto N(x_i|\mu_i(\theta), \sigma_i^2(\theta)) \exp(-\text{spline}(x_i)) \quad (18)$$

where $\pi_{LA}(x_i|\theta, y)$ is the posterior distribution of the latent effects, θ are the hyperparameters of the probability distributions of the latent effects, y are the observations which are related to the linear predictors through some link functions (e.g. identity function), $N()$ is a Gaussian approximation with mean μ_i and σ_i is standard deviation, *spline* is a cubic spline on x_i , y are the observations.

There are used two equations implemented by the INLABRU software package: one equation relates the GDP from agriculture to the climacteric variable (i.e. maximum temperature) as follows:

$$\text{GDP_Agriculture} = a*\text{Credit_to_farmer} + b*\text{Irrigation_area}*\text{Maximum_Temperature} + c*\text{Irrigation_area} + d*\text{Graph_maximum_temperature} + e*\text{Graph_year} + f*\text{ID_iid} \quad (19)$$

where *Graph_maximum_temperature* is a variable of type graph where the nodes are the states and which has as weights the maximum temperature, *Graph_year* is also a variable of type graph representing geographically the states and grouped by year, *ID_iid* accounts for all the independent and identically distributed random variables which it is sure that they exist but are yet unknown in this study, a , b , c , d , e and f are the slopes in eq.(19).

Second equation relates the health outcome to the maximum temperature and the GDP from agriculture with the following equations

$$\text{Health_outcome} = g*\text{Credit_to_farmer} + h*\text{Graph_maximum_temperature} + i*\text{GDP_graph} + j*\text{Graph_year} + k*\text{ID_iid} \quad (20)$$

where GDP_graph is a variable of type graph representing geographically the states (i.e. the geospatial distribution of states) and which has as weights the GDP from agriculture, g, h, i, j and k are the slopes.

Now the direct and indirect effects can be calculated similar as before with the following equations by using the slope h from eq.(20), slope i from eq.(20) and slope d from eq.(19) :

$$\text{Direct_effect} = h \quad (21)$$

$$\text{Indirect_effect} = i * d \quad (22)$$

4. Case studies of climate change impacts on health, economy and environment

The case study shown is with regard to climate change impacts on economy, health and environment for a large geographical area consisting of the country of India and covering also a large size of population of over 100 millions people who are working in the agricultural sector. The agricultural land in India covers presently over 1.78 million square kilometres and therefore such a vast land may suffer because of climate change. Moreover, only about a third of this land has irrigation systems in place. The period of study is of 12 years between 2010 and 2021 and the studied health outcome is pertaining to the death of the humans working in the agricultural sector due to mental health crunch. In total there are 37 Indian states but two states are excluded as they are islands, one state is not relevant for this study and other four states are missing the climate data, which result in 28 states available for this study.

It will be studied how the climate change consisting of increasing of maximum temperatures and/or decreasing of the maximum levels of precipitations affected the economy stability consisting of decreasing of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from agriculture across the same period of time, and which finally might affect the above health outcome. The GDP from agriculture is obtained from the outputs obtained such as from the major crops which are rice (\$70 billion), wheat (\$26 billion), cotton (\$23 billion), mangos/guavas (\$14 billion), fresh vegetables (\$11 billion), potatoes (\$8 billion), banana (\$8 billion), sugar cane (\$7 billion), maize (\$5 billion), oranges (\$5 billion), tomatoes (\$5 billion), chick peas (\$5 billion), okra (\$5 billion) or soybeans (\$5 billion).

4.1 Linear model described in eqs. (1-5)

First model used is the one shown in the DAGs from Figure 13(a) and implemented by eqs. (1-5) and with the maximum temperature per state being used as the confounder variable. The calculated direct and the indirect effects are shown inversely (e.g. $1/\text{direct_effects}$) in Table 2 as they are easier to be understood. The third column shows the total number of events corresponding to the considered health outcome and summed up for the entire period of time 2010 to 2021. Most of the states with relevant health outcomes for the period 2010 to 2021 (i.e. above 200) have also high positive direct effects, which are also shown in bold Haryana (508.58), Karnataka (2080.3), Madhya Pradesh (7181.4), Chhattishgarh (2346.5), Andhra Pradesh (6860.5), Rajasthan (1855.8), Uttar Pradesh (1291.0), and Assam (1327.4): this means that because of the increasing of the maximum temperature in each state during the period of time 2010 to 2021, the health outcomes across these states became worse due to climate change (i.e. the increase of maximum temperature per each state). These other states have also positive direct effects although of lesser magnitude Tripura (84.35), Bihar (131.74), Jharkhand (150.18) and Himachal Pradesh (99.82). In total there are 12 states with positive direct effects, and which were identified also in the list devised above in section 2.4.

Figure 17 shows the maps with the direct and the indirect effects for the Indian states obtained with the DAG from Figure 13(a) and eqs. (1-5).

Table 2. Direct and indirect effects calculated with eqs. (1-5) and DAGs from Figure 2

	Indian state (in bold states with high output rate)	Outcome variable per total (2010- 2021)	Direct effect = $1/\text{Slope}$	Indirect effect = $1/\text{Slope}$ ($\times 10^9$)
1	Andaman & Nicobar	NA	NA	NA
2	Chandigarh	0	NA	NA
3	Daman and Diu and Dadra and Nagar Haveli	78	-62.75	0
4	Delhi	48	28.22	2.05
5	Haryana	1625	508.58	9.37
6	Jharkhand	556	150.18	3.13
7	Karnataka	17607	2080.36	29.68
8	Kerala	4998	-5588.12	-6.50
9	Lakshadweep	NA	NA	NA
10	Madhya Pradesh	9138	7181.43	295.07
11	Maharashtra	36807	-18151.10	247.17
12	Odisha	774	NA	NA
13	Puducherry	34	39.43	0.05
14	Tamilnadu	3476	-18617.01	160.96
15	Chhattishgarh	4422	2346.51	34.19
16	Telengana	6434	-5965.21	-21.54

17	Andhra Pradesh	13517	6860.51	82.73
18	Puducherry	34	39.43	0.05
19	Goa	18	20.35	-1.20
20	Himachal Pradesh	318	99.82	6.48
21	Punjab	1812	-574.80	-38.64
22	Rajasthan	1680	1855.81	154.31
23	Gujarat	3211	NA	NA
24	Uttarakhand	95	21.63	2.34
25	Uttar Pradesh	3671	1291.01	725.73
26	Sikkim	172	-108.79	-0.85
27	Assam	1732	1327.41	16.80
28	Arunachal Pradesh	99	-102.92	-3.94
29	Nagaland	14	14.98	15.34
30	Manipur	10	-3.41	-956.31
31	Mizoram	84	333.71	-29.71
32	Tripura	237	84.35	2.21
33	Meghalaya	67	16.48	0.39
34	West Bengal	2030	NA	NA
35	Bihar	390	131.74	38.45
36	Ladakh	NA	NA	NA
37	Jammu and Kashmir	124	130.32	-9.06

Indirect effect

a) Indirect effect

Direct effect

b) Direct effect

Figure 17. Direct and indirect effects per state obtained with the DAG from Figure 2 and eqs. (1-5).

There are 5 Indian states with important health output rates over the period of time 2010 to 2021: Maharashtra, Tamilnadu, Telengana, Punjab, Kerala (i.e. shown with red colour in Table 2). These 5 states have negative direct effects although they should have had positive direct effects if it is to believe that the climate change took place during the period of time 2010 to 2021 and with bad consequences and effects on the agricultural sector and the health outcome.

In order to find an explanation for the negative direct effects, the maximum temperature per state is replaced in the linear eqs. (1-2) with the maximum precipitation per state, as less precipitation than normal can result in a drier climate (i.e. droughts) and with effects on the economy and the health outcome. Therefore, eqs. (1-5) are used again to investigate the direct effects while using the maximum precipitation per state as confounder: It can be now observed in Figure 18 that the slopes of the fitted lines for when the maximum precipitation is used, had decreased substantially as the health outcome is getting worse (i.e. increasing), which means that lower precipitations (i.e. drier climate, droughts) affected the health outcome. Moreover, Figure 18 shows a comparison between the direct effect results (i.e. slopes) when using the maximum precipitation for the 5 states in the eqs.(1-5) and the direct effect results (i.e. slopes) for when using the maximum temperatures as confounder for the same states: the precipitation slopes are higher than the temperature slopes in Figure 18. This is summarized also in Table 3 below where it can be noticed clearly that 4 states (Telengana, Punjab, Tamilnandu, Maharashtra) have the maximum temperatures decreasing with a smaller percentage than the maximum level of precipitations, and this results in a drier climate and droughts and with effects on the economical agricultural sector and the health outcome.

Table 3. Comparison/study of variations of the maximum temperatures and maximum precipitations for 5 Indian states with relevant health output rates over the period of time between 2010 and 2021, and which 5 Indian states had negative direct effect slopes when using the maximum temperatures per state as confounders as shown in Table 2.

State (time period 2010 - 2021)	Maximum temperature	Comparison between variations of maximum temperatures and maximum precipitations	Maximum precipitation	Real climacteric result
1.Telengana	Maximum temperatures are decreasing with 10%	10% < 42%	Maximum precipitations are decreasing with 42%	Drought
2. Punjab	Maximum temperatures are decreasing with 16%	16% < 37%	Maximum precipitations are decreasing with 37%	Drought
3.Tamilnandu	Maximum temperatures are decreasing 3%	3% < 21%	Maximum precipitations are decreasing with 21%	Drought
4.Maharashtra	Maximum temperatures are decreasing 10%	10% < 32%	Maximum precipitations are decreasing with	Drought

			32% precipitation	
5.Kerala	Maximum temperatures are decreasing with 20%	20% > 7%	Maximum precipitations are decreasing with only 7% (makes an exception)	-

Kerala (i.e. maximum temperatures decreasing with 20% > 7% decreasing maximum precipitation) makes an exception in Table 3 but this might be possible to be explained by the GDP from agriculture of this state, which is smaller than the GDP from agriculture of all the other 12 Indian states (i.e. the positive direct effect ones Haryana, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattishgarh, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, and Assam, plus the 4 negative direct effects ones Telengana, Punjab, Tamilnadu, and Maharashtra). These 12 states have also relevant health outcomes rates (i.e. high number of outcome events), as it can be seen in Table 4.

Therefore, it can be inferred that the state of Kerala is not a representative/relevant state for this study due to its reduced GDP from agriculture income.

The numerical results (i.e. positive direct effects) shown in this section confirmed the expectancy: the increasing of the maximum temperatures during the considered period of time 2010 to 2021 affected the economy in the agricultural sector and affected also the health outcome in the 8 relevant Indian states (Haryana, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattishgarh, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and Assam). By contrasting the results from Table 4 with the list from section 2.4 (Table 1), it results a total of 12 relevant states with positive direct effects.

For other 4 states (Telengana, Punjab, Tamilnadu, Maharashtra), although the direct effect slopes were negative, by using as confounder another climacteric variable consisting of the maximum precipitation, it was possible to determine that these 4 states were also affected by drier climate and droughts conditions and with detrimental consequences on the GDP from agriculture and the considered health outcome (Table 3 and Figure 18).

Table 4. Comparison of GDP from agriculture between Kerala and the other 12 states with significant health outcome (i.e. high number of deaths)

State No.	GDP from agriculture (year 2020)		Kerala (GDP from agriculture year 2020 – the smallest compared to all the other Indian states from third column)
1	Haryana	4.310.271	2.207.388
2	Karnataka	6.674.528	2.207.388
3	Madhya Pradesh	12.788.264	2.207.388
4	Chhattishgarh	2.323.058	2.207.388
5	Andhra Pradesh	7.806.340	2.207.388
6	Uttar Pradesh	14.390.449	2.207.388
7	Assam	2.589.529	2.207.388
8	Rajasthan	8.726.020	2.207.388
9	Maharashtra	10.782.929	2.207.388
10	Tamilnadu	5.050.932	2.207.388
11	Telangana	4.566.183	2.207.388
12	Punjab	5.254.179	2.207.388

a) Telangana: maximum temperature

b) Telangana: maximum precipitation

c) Punjab: maximum temperature

d) Punjab: maximum precipitation

e) Maharashtra: maximum temperature

f) Maharashtra: maximum precipitation

g) Tamilnadu: maximum temperature

h) Tamilnadu: maximum precipitation

i) Kerala: maximum temperature

j) Kerala: maximum precipitation

Figure 18. Comparison between using the maximum temperature and the maximum precipitation as the confounder for the 5 states: Telengana, Punjab, Maharashtra, Tamilnadu, Kerala.

In order to summarize all findings an algorithm is put forward below and consisting of the three steps (Algorithm 1) described above.

- Step 1:1.** Use the maximum temperature as a single input variable (confounder), the health outcome and the linear model to calculate the slopes (i.e. the direct effects);
- 2.** Based on the positive direct effects (i.e. slopes) determined at step 1.1 select the states for which the health outcome is affected by drought: Haryana, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattishgarh, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, and Assam in Table 2.
- Step 2:1.** Use the maximum precipitation as a single input variable (confounder), the health outcome and the linear model for the relevant states with negative direct effects from Table 2 in order to calculate some new direct effects (slopes) based this time on the maximum precipitation as confounder;
- 2.** Compare now the maximum precipitation decreased with the maximum temperature decreased and if it is higher (maximum precipitation decreased > maximum temperature decreased) then it results a drought for the respective states (i.e. Table 3 and Figure 18): Maharashtra, Tamilnadu, Telengana, Punjab.
- Step 3:** For the states that have negative direct effects calculated at step 1 and have the maximum precipitation decreased lower than the maximum temperature decreased (i.e. possibly not affected by drought) compare the GDP from agriculture of these states with the GDP from agriculture of the states identified at Steps 1 and 2 (Table 4): Kerala.

Algorithm 1. Algorithm based on the calculated direct effects to identify all the possible states affected adversely by climate change.

In terms of positive indirect effects, there were identified 14 states with positive indirect effects: Haryana, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamilnadu, Chhattishgarh, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Assam, Tripura, Bihar and Himachal Pradesh.

4.2 Multiple linear model implemented by eqs. (6-9) and using the maximum temperature per state as confounder

The multiple linear model described in eqs. (6-9) are used to calculate the direct and the indirect effects. As confounder representing the climate change is used the maximum temperature, but other variables could be used such as maximum precipitation or SPEI index.

Although this model is slightly more intricate than the previous one from section 4.1, it is still possible to see in Table 5 that there are positive direct effects of the maximum temperatures on the health outcome and positive indirect effects of the maximum temperatures on the health outcome via the GDP from agriculture mediator. There are similarities with the results from the previous section (Table 2) with positive direct effects for Karnataka, Chhattishgarh, Andhra Pradesh, Jharkhand, Bihar, Uttar Pradesh but also other states like Himachal Pradesh, Punjab and Tripura. Overall, by contrasting the results from Table 5 with the list from section 2.4 (Table 1), it results a total of 9 relevant states with positive direct effects: Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Chhattishgarh, Jharkhand, Himachal Pradesh, Bihar, Tripura, Punjab.

Positive indirect effects are for the following 8 states: Haryana, Karnataka, Rajasthan, Jharkhand, Himachal Pradesh, Tripura, Bihar, Assam. Once again, positive indirect or direct effects correspond to positive slopes (i.e. coefficients) in the multiple linear model, which indicate that for an increase in the maximum temperatures per each state there will be then a worsening situation for the health outcome.

Statistics of the multiple linear model implemented by eq.(7) can be inspected in Table A2 (Appendix): it can be seen that for the states with relevant health outcome, the F-statistics of the multiple linear model is under 2.5 and the p-values are under 0.05 and therefore the models are considered to be statistical significant for these states: Haryana, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Goa, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, Jharkhand, Meghalaya, Punjab, Sikkim, Rajasthan, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Delhi and Assam. Other states like Karnataka (F =1.903, p-value = 0.2) and Maharashtra (F = 2.27, p-value =0.1585), which are relevant for this study, have also statistical values not far away from the thresholds of 2.5 (F) and 0.05 (p).

Figure 19 shows the direct and the indirect effects on the map of the respective country.

Table 5. Direct and indirect effects calculated with eqs. (6-9) and DAGs from Figure 14 and using the maximum temperature as a confounder.

State No	Indian state (in bold the states with high output variable)	Outcome variable per total (2010-2021)	Direct effect (slope)	Indirect effect
1	Andaman & Nicobar	NA	NA	NA
2	Chandigarh	0	NA (output is zero)	NA
3	Daman and Diu and Dadra and Nagar Haveli	78	NA	NA
4	Delhi	48	-0.18	2.87
5	Haryana	1625	-48.94	233.70

6	Jharkhand	556	53.78	19.70
7	Karnataka	17607	221.71	24.08
8	Kerala	4998	-93.95	-181.99
9	Lakshadweep	NA	NA	NA
10	Madhya Pradesh	9138	-61.73	-87.12
11	Maharashtra	36807	-103.33	-93.72
12	Odisha	774	NA (temperature not available)	NA
13	Puducherry	34	2.15	1.84
14	Tamilnadu	3476	-195.02	-84.53
15	Chhattishgarh	4422	109.21	-15.42
16	Telengana	6434	-131.52	-35.36
17	Andhra Pradesh	13517	461.46	-248.35
18	Puducherry	34	2.15	1.84
19	Goa	18	4.36	-1.91
20	Himachal Pradesh	318	8.39	10.26
21	Punjab	1812	60.38	-94.70
22	Rajasthan	1680	-18.83	26.94
23	Gujarat	3211	NA (temperature not available)	NA
24	Uttarakhand	95	6.20	4.83
25	Uttar Pradesh	3671	134.56	-87.44
26	Sikkim	172	2.32	-8.97
27	Assam	1732	-12.01	37.87
28	Arunachal Pradesh	99	0.13	-3.72
29	Nagaland	14	2.04	0.54
30	Manipur	10	-0.49	-0.01
31	Mizoram	84	2.24	-1.42
32	Tripura	237	4.90	8.21
33	Meghalaya	67	-0.65	3.17
34	West Bengal	2030	NA (temperature not available)	NA
35	Bihar	390	19.91	11.25
36	Ladakh	NA	NA	NA
37	Jammu and Kashmir	124	3.34	-1.72

Figure 19. Direct and indirect effects per state obtained with the DAG from Figure 14 and eqs. (6-9) and using the maximum temperature as a confounder.

Interpretation of direct and indirect effects

Once again the sign of the direct and indirect effects have a similar interpretation as the one given in the previous section (i.e. section 4.1). With the parameters (i.e. slopes and intercept) of the eqs. (6-9) calculated in this section and for which the results are shown in Figure 19 and Table 5, and for several relevant Indian states (i.e. Andra Pradesh, Karnataka and Maharashtra), there are shown in the APPENDIX (Figure A1, Figure A2, Figure A3) for these relevant Indian states (Andra Pradesh , Karnataka and Maharashtra) the simulation of their multiple linear regression equations of the following type:

$$\text{Health_Outcome} = \text{intercept} + a \text{ Maximum_Temperature} + b \text{ GDP_Agriculture} \quad (23)$$

which is bivariate model with two independent variables (Maximum_Temperature, GDP_Agriculture).

These multiple linear regression simulations result in three plots, each plot being of 3-dimensional size, and which are shown in Figure A1 (Maharashtra), Figure A2 (Karnataka) and in Figure A3 (Andra Pradesh). Each 3-dimensional plot (e.g. Figure A1) shows a plane, and on the z-axis is the health outcome while on the other axes there are the Maximum_Temperature and the GDP_Agriculture. It can be seen that when the slope (direct effect) of the maximum temperature is a positive number such as for the states Andra Pradesh and Karnataka, then if the temperature increases then the health outcome increases as

well, as it can be seen in the Fig.A2 and Fig.A. If the health outcomes (i.e. the three dimensional planes) are shown from a side, they look rather like a straight line going from a lower value of 1600 towards a higher value of 1900 for example for Karnataka (Fig.A2b).

Furthermore, when the slope of temperature is negative (e.g. -103.33; direct effect) as it is the case of Indian state Maharashtra, it means that when the maximum temperature increases then the health outcome value decreases as it can be seen in the Figure A1. If the health outcome (i.e. the 3-dimensional plane) is shown from a side, it looks rather again like a straight line going from a higher value of approximately 3600 towards a lower value of 3500. In other words, the predicted value of health outcome changes by value of "a" (i.e. direct effect/slope) for each one unit increase in variable Maximum_Temperatrue when all other variables are constant (i.e. GDP_agriculture).

4.3 Multiple linear model implemented by eqs. (6-9) and using the yearly minimum SPEI index per state as a confounder

The multiple linear model described in eqs. (6-9) is used again to calculate the direct and the indirect effects, only that now for the confounder representing the climate change is used the yearly minimum SPEI index so that to make a comparison with the results from the previous section 4.2. For each year between 2010 and 2021 it is used for each 28 states the yearly minimum value of SPEI index because lower index values correspond to drier climates (i.e. droughts), while higher index values correspond to humid climate, while we are interested in this work in climate changes consisting of drier climates and droughts.

Table 6 and Figure 20 show the direct and the indirect effects obtained with the multiple linear model implemented by eqs.(6-9) and using also the yearly minimum SPEI index per state as a confounder. By contrasting the results from Table 6 with the list from section 2.4, it results a total of 12 relevant states with positive direct effects: Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Uttar Pradesh, Tamilnadu, Punjab, Assam, Rajasthan, Haryana, Jharkhand, Himachal Pradesh, Tripura. This reimplementation identified 6 states with positive indirect effects: Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Telengana, Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Tripura.

Table 6. Direct and indirect effects calculated with eqs. (6-9) and DAGs from Fig. 14 and using also the yearly minimum SPEI index per state as a confounder.

State No	Indian state (in bold the states with high output variable)	Outcome variable per total (2010-2021)	Direct effect (slope)	Indirect effect
1	Andaman & Nicobar	NA	NA	NA
2	Chandigarh	0	NA (output is zero)	NA
3	Daman and Diu and Dadra and Nagar Haveli	78	NA	NA
4	Delhi	48	-1.12	2.22
5	Haryana	1625	55.37	-19.53
6	Jharkhand	556	3.48	-19.76
7	Karnataka	17607	73.43	-184.52
8	Kerala	4998	72.91	344.19
9	Lakshadweep	NA	NA	NA
10	Madhya Pradesh	9138	-210.40	205.72
11	Maharashtra	36807	-454.87	-24.41
12	Odisha	774	NA (temperature not available)	NA
13	Puducherry	34	-5.06	-1.46
14	Tamilnadu	3476	68.20	-11.57
15	Chhattishgarh	4422	-59.79	-9.40
16	Telengana	6434	-458.62	465.13
17	Andhra Pradesh	13517	324.67	-634.19
18	Puducherry	34	-5.06	-1.46
19	Goa	18	8.60	-1.35
20	Himachal Pradesh	318	8.60	11.29
21	Punjab	1812	1.89	17.03
22	Rajasthan	1680	24.12	-19.18
23	Gujarat	3211	NA (temperature not available)	NA
24	Uttarakhand	95	-1.06	-1.16
25	Uttar Pradesh	3671	132.14	-121.93
26	Sikkim	172	-3.92	14.37
27	Assam	1732	3.43	-112.42
28	Arunachal Pradesh	99	7.15	2.13
29	Nagaland	14	-3.24	0.0028
30	Manipur	10	-0.45	0.264
31	Mizoram	84	-8.15	-0.324
32	Tripura	237	8.74	3.89
33	Meghalaya	67	-0.72	-1.36
34	West Bengal	2030	NA (temperature not available)	NA
35	Bihar	390	-12.02	-18.85
36	Ladakh	NA	NA	NA
37	Jammu and Kashmir	124	13.83	3.07

Indirect effect

a) Indirect effect

Direct effect

b) Direct effect

Figure 20. Direct and indirect effects per state obtained with the DAG from Fig.14 and eqs. (6-9) and using also the yearly minimum SPEI index per state as a confounder.

4.4 Complex DAG multiple linear model implemented by eqs. (10-13)

The complex DAG (Fig.16(a)) of the multiple linear model implemented in eqs. (10-13) is used to calculate the direct and the indirect effects. Table 7 shows the direct effects of the maximum temperatures on the health outcome and the indirect effects of the maximum temperatures on the health outcome via the GDP from agriculture mediator. There are again similarities with the initial results from the Table 2 with positive direct effects for Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Tripura although the total number of states with positive direct or indirect effects/slopes have now decreased. The decrease in the number of states with positive direct/indirect effects means that as more variables (i.e. risks, moderators) are added into the DAG multiple linear model, then the interactions between all variables become more non-linear and the effects of the independent variable on the health outcome become more difficult to be identified because of these non-linear interactions.

In total by contrasting the results from Table 7 with the list from section 2.4 (Table 1), it results a total of 6 relevant states with positive direct effects: Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, Bihar, Tripura. There are 8 states with positive indirect effects, which are Jharkhand, Karnataka, Tamilnadu, Telengana, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Tripura and Bihar.

This model identified 8 states with positive indirect effects: Jharkhand, Karnataka, Tamilnadu, Telengana, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Tripura, Bihar.

Fig. 21 shows the direct and the indirect effects obtained with the complex DAG multiple linear model: the indirect effects are shown divided by value 60 hence the term min (i.e. minute) in the Fig.21.

For comparison purposes, the DAG from Fig.16(b) and the multiple linear model implemented in eqs. (14-15) is used to calculate the indirect effects shown in Table 7 on the sixth column. This is the case where the irrigation area variable is a risk variable instead of a moderator variable. The indirect effect results show some degree of similarity between when using the irrigation area variable either as a moderator variable (Fig.16(a)) or as a risk variable (Fig.16(b)).

Table 7. Direct and indirect effects calculated with eqs. (10-13) and DAGs from Fig. 16(a).

	Indian state (in bold the states with high output variable)	Outcome variable per total (2010- 2021)	Direct effect (slope)	Indirect effect (Fig.16a)	Indirect effect (Fig.16(b) and eqs.(14-15))
1	Andaman & Nicobar	NA	0	0	0
2	Chandigarh	0	NA	NA	NA
3	Daman and Diu and Dadra and Nagar Haveli	78	NA	NA	NA
4	Delhi	48	-1.39	-2.86	-2.28
5	Haryana	1625	-85.01	-768.42	-1753.02
6	Jharkhand	556	-0.86	938.00	659.50
7	Karnataka	17607	264.92	3347.86	1862.61
8	Kerala	4998	-176.12	-1748.29	-1706.57
9	Lakshadweep	NA	NA	NA	NA
10	Madhya Pradesh	9138	-133.76	-13041.53	-12379.01
11	Maharashtra	36807	-131.82	-5723.90	-11375.77
12	Odisha	774	NA	NA	NA

13	Puducherry	34	1.69	3.72	3.40
14	Tamilnadu	3476	-73.675	1412.86	719.82
15	Chhattishgarh	4422	-26.17	-20242.07	-25512.36
16	Telengana	6434	-518.62	9121.68	7470.98
17	Andhra Pradesh	13517	446.33	-5545.57	-48994.44
18	Puducherry	34	1.69	3.72	3.40
19	Goa	18	3.03	-222.42	-194.27
20	Himachal Pradesh	318	-1.89	-466.93	-505.37
21	Punjab	1812	61.12	0.39	125.27
22	Rajasthan	1680	-22.23	-187.40	-326.30
23	Gujarat	3211	NA	NA	NA
24	Uttarakhand	95	-0.77	-278.50	-334.29
25	Uttar Pradesh	3671	134.57	0.51	0.52
26	Sikkim	172	-2.70	2166.98	1871.69
27	Assam	1732	-15.28	-987.06	-434.03
28	Arunachal Pradesh	99	-4.34	-6427.09	-3736.69
29	Nagaland	14	2.05	-11.57	-5.85
30	Manipur	10	-0.34	101.75	115.08
31	Mizoram	84	2.44	14.65	27.64
32	Tripura	237	8.42	403.42	-189.51
33	Meghalaya	67	-0.37	43.52	30.88
34	West Bengal	2030	NA	NA	NA
35	Bihar	390	6.45	36.16	-231.89
36	Ladakh	NA	0.00	0.00	0
37	Jammu and Kashmir	124	1.81	-91.59	-66.57

Indirect effect

a) Indirect effects

Direct effect

b) Direct effects

Figure 21. Direct and indirect effects per state obtained with the DAG from Fig. 16(a) and eqs. (10-13).

4.5 Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation with Bayesian Regression Univariate software model implemented by eqs. (16-22)

The fourth model is INLABRU point processes software model, which is designed especially for making inference for the output variables (e.g. health outcomes) which are spatially correlated. Table 8 shows the direct effects obtained with the INLABRU software model for the maximum temperatures on the health outcome and the indirect effects of the maximum temperatures on the health outcome via the GDP from agriculture mediator, and once again for the DAG from Fig.16(a).

There are similarities with the results shown in Table 2 with positive direct effects for states with high outputs like Haryana, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattishgarh, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Assam although the INLABRU software model can identify other states with positive direct effects such as Kerala, Maharashtra and Telengana. In total there are 12 states obtained by contrasting the results from Table 8 with the list from chapter 2.4 (Table 1): Maharashtra, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Telengana, Kerala, Chhattishgarh, Uttar Pradesh, Tamilnadu, Assam, Rajasthan, Haryana.

In terms of positive indirect effects there are identified 6 states: Haryana, Karnataka, Kerala, Telengana, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan.

Table 8. Direct and indirect effects calculated with eqs. (16-22) and INLABRU software model for the DAG from Figure 16(a).

	Indian state	Outcome variable per total (2010-2021)	Direct effects	Indirect effects
1	Andaman & Nicobar	NA	NA	NA
2	Chandigarh	0	NA	NA
3	Daman and Diu and Dadra and Nagar Haveli	78	-1.86	0.018
4	Delhi	48	0.71	-0.07
5	Haryana	1625	6.47	0.4
6	Jharkhand	556	0.10	-0.06
7	Karnataka	17607	42.62	0.1
8	Kerala	4998	26.84	1.83
9	Lakshadweep	NA	NA	NA
10	Madhya Pradesh	9138	33.42	-1.83
11	Maharashtra	36807	78.40	-1.47
12	Odisha	774	NA	NA

13	Puducherry	34	-1.78	0.1
14	Tamilnadu	3476	16.65	-2.21
15	Chhattishgarh	4422	9.22	-0.03
16	Telengana	6434	5.27	0.1
17	Andhra Pradesh	13517	66.25	3.53
18	Puducherry	34	-1.90	0.005
19	Goa	18	-1.94	0.08
20	Himachal Pradesh	318	-1.38	-0.01
21	Punjab	1812	-3.39	-3.19
22	Rajasthan	1680	7.85	0.02
23	Gujarat	3211	NA	NA
24	Uttarakhand	95	-1.47	-0.04
25	Uttar Pradesh	3671	15.14	-0.1
26	Sikkim	172	-2.46	-0.04
27	Assam	1732	4.26	-0.6
28	Arunachal Pradesh	99	-3.93	1.51
29	Nagaland	14	-2.73	-0.06
30	Manipur	10	-2.62	-0.06
31	Mizoram	84	-2.47	-0.07
32	Tripura	237	-2.05	-0.05
33	Meghalaya	67	-2.49	-0.07
34	West Bengal	2030	NA	NA
35	Bihar	390	-0.05	-0.2
36	Ladakh	NA	NA	NA
37	Jammu and Kashmir	124	-2.25	-0.03

Indirect effect

a) Indirect effects

Direct effect

b) Direct effects

Figure 22. Direct and indirect effects per state obtained with the DAG from Fig.16(a) and eqs. (16-22) implementing INLABRU software package.

5. Discussion and conclusions

This paper used causal inference methods (DAG) and Bayesian regression models in order to study the climate change impacts on the economy and health. In total there were compared four models plus a reimplementing of the second model by using the SPEI index. The models differed by their complexity in terms of both the mathematical formulation and the number of variables used. In total there were developed 4 models, while the 2nd model was reimplemented by using the yearly minimum SPEI index as input variable.

First model (section 4.1) consisted of the simplest linear model consisting of a linear equation in order to evaluate the direct effect of a single independent variable (maximum temperature or maximum precipitation) on the health outcome: 12 states were identified as having positive direct effects. Furthermore, an algorithm was devised so that to look also to several other 5 states, which had negative direct effects, and which algorithm was able to identify 4 states from the 5 states as being affected by drought.

The second model (section 4.2) used an independent variable (maximum temperature) and a mediator variable (GPD from agriculture) to assess the effects on the health outcome by using two linear equations.

A reimplementing of the second model was done in section 4.3 and the confounder was the yearly minimum SPEI index.

A third and more complex model (section 4.4) used an independent variable (maximum temperature), a mediator variable (GPD from agriculture), a risk variable (credit to farmer) and a moderator variable (irrigation area) to assess the effects on the health outcome by using several linear equations.

Finally, the fourth model (section 4.5) relied on Bayesian regression implemented by the INLABRU software package and it used an independent variable (maximum temperature), a mediator variable (GPD from agriculture), a risk variable (credit to farmer) and a moderator variable (irrigation area) in order to assess the effects on the health outcome.

All models are summarized in Table 9 and it includes the sections in the paper where the results were obtained and shown.

Model	Section	Type of model	Input variable
1	4.1	Linear	Step1. Maximum Temperature Step2. Maximum Precipitation Step3. GDP agriculture
2	4.2	Multiple linear model	Maximum Temperature
2-reimplementation	4.3	Multiple linear model	SPEI index yearly minimum
3	4.4	Complex multiple linear model	Maximum Temperature
4	4.5	INLABRU	Maximum Temperature

Table 9. Models developed for calculation of direct and indirect effects.

Direct effects

The results show some level of similarity through all the four developed methods plus the reimplementation from section 4.3 using the yearly minimum SPEI index, as they all identified several important agricultural states (Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh) with positive high direct effects on the health outcome because of climate change.

Due to the simplicity of the first model (section 4.1) and also because of the careful selection and intelligent use of the independent climacteric variables (maximum temperature and maximum precipitation), it was possible to successfully detect the influence that the climate change has on the economy and the health outcome for all the agricultural relevant Indian states: Haryana, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattishgarh, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and Assam. Other four states (Telengana, Punjab, Tamilnadu, Maharashtra) were identified by a comparison of their direct effect slopes between when using the maximum temperature and the maximum precipitation on the health outcome. It was observed steeper decreasing slopes for when using the maximum precipitation than for when using the maximum temperatures. This made a total of 12 states with positive direct effects plus other 4 states identified based on maximum precipitation and maximum temperature.

A single state (Kerala) was identified as possible not relevant for this study because of its reduced revenues from agriculture (GDP from agriculture) when compared with the other eight plus four (i.e. 12) states.

The second model, which is the multiple linear model using the maximum temperature as the confounder, identified 9 states with positive direct effects: Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Chhattishgarh, Jharkhand, Himachal Pradesh, Bihar, Tripura, Punjab.

Furthermore, in terms of positive direct effects, the reimplementation of the second model using the yearly minimum SPEI index (i.e. section 4.3) identified 12 Indian states with positive direct effects: Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Uttar Pradesh, Tamilnadu, Punjab, Assam, Rajasthan, Haryana, Jharkhand, Himachal Pradesh, Tripura.

The third model (i.e. section 4.4: 6 Indian states identified with positive direct effects), which was also more complex in its formulation, was able to identify the least number of states in terms of positive direct effects (6): Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, Bihar, Tripura.

The fourth model, which was INLABRU (i.e. section 4.5), identified 12 Indian states with positive direct effects due to the climate changes: Maharashtra, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Telengana, Kerala, Chhattishgarh, Uttar Pradesh, Tamilnadu, Assam, Rajasthan, Haryana.

Table 10 summarizes these findings together with the calculated total score for each model, which total score was calculated based on the summation of each individual score obtained by each state from the following descending list which was devised initially in section 2.4 of this paper: Maharashtra (20), Karnataka (19), Andhra Pradesh (18), Madhya Pradesh (17), Telengana (16), Kerala (15), Chhattishgarh (14), Uttar Pradesh (13), Tamilnadu (12), Gujarat (11), West Bengal (10), Punjab (9), Assam (8), Rajasthan (7), Haryana (6), Odisha (5), Jharkhand (4), Himachal Pradesh (3), Bihar (2), Tripura (1). A partial score is also calculated based only on the first five states (Maharashtra (20), Karnataka (19), Andhra Pradesh (18), Madhya Pradesh (17), Telengana (16)), which are the most relevant for this study because of their biggest health output numbers shown in Table 1.

Based on the total score, the INLABRU model (score=165) followed by the 2nd model re-implemented using the yearly minimum SPEI index (score=115) and the 1st model (score=112), are the models with the highest scores based on the positive direct effects.

Model	Paper Section	Type of model and input variable(s)	Positive Direct effects	Total score	Partial score
1	4.1	Linear (Step1. Maximum Temperature) (Step2. Maximum Precipitation) (Step3. GDP agriculture)	12	112	90

2	4.2	Multiple linear model (Maximum Temperature)	9	83	37
2- reimplementation	4.3	Multiple linear model (SPEI index yearly minimum)	12	115	37
3	4.4	Complex multiple linear model (Maximum Temperature)	6	53	37
4	4.5	INLABRU (Maximum Temperature)	12	165	90

Table 10. Models developed and the number of Indian states with the positive direct effects.

Indirect effects

The four developed models can measure the direct effects but also the indirect health effects of climate change amidst unseen influencing factors (i.e. INLABRU software model) as it used real data (i.e. India) including temperatures, precipitation, GDP from agriculture, size of irrigated land, debts of farmers or number of deaths of the farmers due to a mental health crunch.

First model identified 14 states with positive indirect effects: Haryana, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamilnadu, Chhattishgarh, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Assam, Tripura, Bihar and Himachal Pradesh.

Second model identified 8 states with positive indirect effects: Haryana, Karnataka, Rajasthan, Jharkhand, Himachal Pradesh, Tripura, Bihar, Assam.

The reimplementation of the second model with SPEI index identified 6 states with positive indirect effects: Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Telengana, Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Tripura.

The complex multiple linear model with maximum temperature as confounder identified 8 states with positive indirect effects: Jharkhand, Karnataka, Tamilnadu, Telengana, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Tripura, Bihar.

The last model (INLABRU) identified 6 states with positive indirect effects: Haryana, Karnataka, Kerala, Telengana, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan.

Table 11 summarizes the models developed and the total number of Indian states with positive indirect effects. Based again on the total scores calculated from the summation of each individual score of each state from the descending list which was devised initially in

section 2.4 of this paper (i.e. Table 1), it results the following order of models with the highest score corresponding to the most valuable model in terms of positive indirect effects: the first model (score=144), the INLABRU model (score=81), the 2nd model re-implemented using the yearly minimum SPEI index (score=76) and the third model implementing the complex multiple linear model with the SPEI index as input variable/confounder (76).

-Model	Paper Section	Type of model	Positive Indirect effects	Total score	Partial Score
1	4.1	Linear (Step1. Maximum Temperature) (Step2. Maximum Precipitation) (Step3. GDP agriculture)	14	144	74
2	4.2	Multiple linear model (Maximum Temperature)	8	50	19
2- reimplementation	4.3	Multiple linear model (SPEI index yearly minimum)	6	61	33
3	4.4	Complex multiple linear model (Maximum Temperature)	8	76	34
4	4.5	INLABRU (Maximum Temperature)	6	81	53

Table 11. Models developed, the number of Indian states with the positive indirect effects and the total score of each model.

Software application

Furthermore, an interactive software application has been developed, which can work both off-line or on-line and which highlights the interconnected effects of climate change on health and the economy in order to inform policy decisions. The developed models and the software application demonstrate the potential to illuminate the complex interactions between climate change, economy, and health. It was shown that the climate change indirectly impacts health via economic effects, a relationship complicated by unseen factors that might skew the understanding of the policymakers regardless of whether it is used statistical models or machine learning. The results show that focusing on health issues not directly tied to climate change, such as mental health problems in farming communities, provides a clearer picture.

These mental health problems have been also recently included in a larger class of diseases termed ‘Disease of Despair’ (DoD) in the farming communities. As these DoD diseases are unlikely to be directly influenced by weather changes, it simplifies the complex subject, aiding the comprehension of the interconnectedness of climate change, economy, and mental health problems and DoD.

Future work will consist in applying the methods developed on this paper to other case studies and also for different health outcomes such as death due to primary biliary cirrhosis due alcohol consumption (i.e. alcoholism), which is also part of DoD.

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APPENDIX

Table A1. Variables (confounders, risks, moderators, mediator)

Variable	Factor	Availability	Notes	References
Maximum temperature	Exposure	Yes	Higher temperatures for longer periods of time will produce drought, which will affect directly the health of agriculture workers and indirectly by destroying the economy and in consequence affecting again the wealth and health of agriculture workers.	[8,47,50,51,53,109]
Scale of agriculture	Risk	No	Smaller land based agriculture is more difficult to be sustained economically by government and the lower productivity can affect the GDP from agriculture and the economy: small land holdings stop benefiting from mechanization, modern irrigation, and other investment-based technological improvements.	[52,110,111,112, 115]
Irrigation area	Moderator	Yes	Better irrigation systems and larger areas being irrigated would protect the crops from the consequences of droughts consisting of	[54,55,52,70,100, 112]

			lack of water which is necessary to the crops.	
GDP from Agriculture	Mediator	Yes		
Education of farmers	Risk	No	Better educated farmers (including literacy and ICT use) may give the farmers the opportunity to - to be better informed about the agricultural market; -to have and to use the best knowledge and management practices with regard crops; -to manage their lives better including their own health; -to gain better access to other/better funds, credits and loan facilities.	[51,52,108,112]
Diseases of Despair	Outcome	Yes		[68]
Maximum precipitation	Exposure	Yes	Lower precipitation for longer periods of time may favour droughts, which will affect directly the health of agriculture workers and indirectly by destroying the economy and in consequence affecting again the wealth and health of agriculture workers.	[8,47,50,51,53,70,109]
Characteristics of the crops	Risk	No	Cash crops (i.e. any agricultural crop	[57,113,114]

			<p>grown to sell on the market rather than for personal use or consumption by the producer) involve higher costs, cash crop cultivators, with marginal landholdings and debts are most at risk as opposed to food crops.</p>	
Type of crop (i.e. rice, beans, etc)	Moderator	No	<p>Some crops are more affected by droughts/floods than other crops.</p> <p>These are characteristics of crops which may or may not protect the farmers from climate change and the subsequent economical problems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>Crop management</u> practices in the area of (perceived soil quality conditions, <u>irrigation system</u>, water saving practices, fertilization, pest and disease control, weed control, property management); - Changing Cropping Intensity (e.g. changing land use practices); -Crop failure – some crops are more resistant to droughts and lack of water than other crops; - Distance between crop area and the 	[47,52,112,127,128,134]

			output market.	
Characteristics of the market(s)	Risk	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unfavourable market prices for crops and livestock; - Fair price for farm products must be ensured, and middlemen eliminated by creating a direct reach for the farmers to the market; - The government-administered MSP (Minimum Support Price) should take into consideration the existing realities to cover the cost of production and to insulate farmers from fluctuating market conditions. -Comprehensive but affordable insurance schemes should be made available, covering farmers and crops from problems at every stage of the crop cycle. -Marketly orientation to some specific products in the detriment of other agricultural products. - Poor access to market information 	[48,49,95-99]
Standardized Precipitation and Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI)	Exposure	Yes	-The same as above: lower negative SPEI index correspond to droughts, which will affect directly the health of agriculture	[8,47,50,51,53,109]

			workers and indirectly by destroying the economy and in consequence affecting again the wealth and health of agriculture workers.	
Agricultural incentives	Risk	No	<p>Higher levels of incentives given by the government to the agriculture may support the lives of the farmers a)directly by using more modern agriculture, and which will decrease the chances of accidents, and b)indirectly by better productivity and better economical prospects, which will support the health status of farmers.</p> <p>Types of incentives: -four kinds of incentives are evaluated Agri-Environment Schemes (AES)/Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES), input subsidies, direct subsidies, and market-based incentives.</p>	[70,123-126]
Wealth	Moderator	No	<p>Richer agriculture workers would have more money to defend from:</p> <p>a) The direct effects of the climate change on their health (e.g.</p>	[70-74]

			<p>by using modern agriculture such as benefiting from mechanization, modern agriculture machines with air conditioning), and</p> <p>b) Indirectly because of the economical effects of crops destruction because of</p> <p>c) Richer farmers would have more money and be able to defend from poor credit/loan facilities.</p>	
Comorbidities of farmers	Risk	No	<p>Poor physical health/past injuries: neck, shoulder, and back pain , obesity, metabolic syndrome, abdominal adiposity, cardiovascular disease, higher body mass index (BMI) and poor sleep quality, musculoskeletal disorders, cuts, fractures, organophosphate poisoning, previous mental disorders (anxiety, depression, stress).</p>	[8]
Credit to farmers from legal (i.e. bank, funds) or illegal sources (i.e. private persons)	Exposure	Yes	<p>- Unperformant credits to farmer may affect a) directly the health of farmers and b) indirectly the economy and GDP with consequences also on the health of farmers.</p>	[8,70,93,94]

Climate adaptation support	Risk	No	Comprehensive but affordable bank or government insurance schemes or simply government support should be made available so that to cover farmers and crops from climate problems at every stage of the crop cycle.	[116-122]
Type of worker	Risk	No	<p>Three types of farming can be Identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -family farming -corporate farming -patronal farming (family plus contracted people by the family). <p>a) Cultivators = farmers who supervise the land they own or rent.</p> <p>b) Agricultural labourers = the labourers who work on other's farms on daily wages.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Farmer Land owner can be classified as large farmers, medium farmers, semi-medium farmers, small farmers, and marginal or micro-farmers; - Employed worker 	[129-133]

Table A2. Statistics of the multiple linear model implemented by eq.(7)

No.	State	Outcome variable per total (2010-2021)	F statistics model (good > 2.5)	p-value (< 0.05)
1	Andhra Pradesh	13517	9.784	0.005528
2	Arunachal Pradesh	99	1.314	0.3157
3	Assam	1732	8.723	0.007825
4	Bihar	390	6.633	0.01697
5	Chandigarh	0	NA	NA
6	Chhattisgarh	4422	0.4118	0.6743
7	Dadra and Nagar Haveli and Daman and Diu	78	NA	NA
8	Goa	18	4.481	0.04461
9	Gujarat	3211	NA	NA
10	Haryana	1625	20.85	0.0004185
11	Himachal Pradesh	318	4.261	0.04988
12	Jammu and Kashmir	124	2.92	0.1054
13	Jharkhand	556	4.917	0.03604
14	Karnataka	17607	1.903	0.2045
15	Kerala	4998	40.77	0.0000308
16	Lakshadweep	NA	NA	NA
17	Madhya Pradesh	9138	17.31	0.0008233
18	Maharashtra	36807	2.276	0.1585
19	Manipur	10	0.8634	0.4539
20	Meghalaya	67	12.41	0.002588
21	Mizoram	84	0.00495	0.9951
22	Nagaland	14	1.876	0.2084
23	Odisha	774	NA	NA
24	Punjab	1812	40.38	0.00003202
25	Rajasthan	1680	50.48	0.00001284
26	Sikkim	172	4.586	0.04235
27	Tamil Nadu	3476	1.485	0.2771
28	Telangana	6434	0.1689	0.8472
29	Tripura	237	5.539	0.02703
30	Uttar Pradesh	3671	17.64	0.0007696
31	Uttarakhand	95	8.518	0.008394
32	West Bengal	2030	NA	NA
33	NCT of Delhi	48	4.705	0.03994
34	Puducherry	34	1.78	0.2232

a) Panoramic view.

b) Side view.

Figure A1. Slope of the multiple linear regression equation of the type $\text{Health_Outcome} = \text{intercept} + \text{Slope1} \times \text{Maximum_Temperature} + \text{Slope2} \times \text{GDP_Agriculture}$ (i.e. bivariate model with two independent variables) for the Indian state of Maharashtra.

a) Panoramic view.

b) Side view.

Figure A2. Slope of the multiple linear regression equation of the type $\text{Health_Outcome} = \text{intercept} + \text{Slope1} \times \text{Maximum_Temperature} + \text{Slope2} \times \text{GDP_Agriculture}$ (i.e. bivariate model with two independent variables) for the Indian state of Karnataka.

a) Panoramic view.

b) Side view.

Figure A3. Slope of the multiple linear regression equation of the type $\text{Health_Outcome} = \text{intercept} + \text{Slope1} \times \text{Maximum_Temperature} + \text{Slope2} \times \text{GDP_Agriculture}$ (i.e. bivariate model with two independent variables) for the Indian state of Andhra Pradesh.

